
DISCLAIMER

This is not a peer-reviewed paper, and none of the taxonomic decisions presented here are valid or scientifically binding.

On 1st April 2025, I (VT) uploaded an informal research article to **Zenodo** and **ResearchGate**, wherein I elaborated on my insights after reviewing past papers of the genus *Heteronebo* Pocock, 1899 and examining a new immature specimen from Socotra, Yemen. I proposed a new genus, *Aposanguis*, to differentiate the Socotran species (for which the genus was created) from the later-described Caribbean species, based mainly on paleogeographic evidence. I also provisionally considered *H. forbesii* as a junior synonym of *H. granti* given the intermediate morphology exhibited by the new specimen, their narrow distribution, and the ambiguities in their presumed diagnostic characters due to the lack of photographs. All of these taxonomic decisions were held informal and unsettled owing to the practical requirement of an extensive review of all congeners currently still included within this genus and the inherent uncertainty in purely literature-based inference. Thereafter, my friend (MW) and I had been waiting for the opportunity to reexamine the type series of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* deposited in the Natural History Museum, United Kingdom (NHMUK). On 20th June 2025, MW managed to take most of the photographs I required. After processing the photos and arranging them into plates, I wrote this new, informal article, serving as the supplement to the earlier one. Given the informal nature of both articles, they do not affect the current taxonomic status of the discussed species, representing merely my exploratory studies on these enigmatic taxa.

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Reappraisal on the genus *Heteronebo* Pocock, 1899 (Scorpiones: Diplocentridae)

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Summary

Re-examination of the lectotypes and paralectotypes of *Heteronebo forbesii* Pocock, 1899 and *H. granti* Pocock, 1899 confirmed the taxonomic validity of both species, with key diagnostic characters highlighted. Photographs of these specimens are provided for the first time. Comments are given on the species diagnostics of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti*, ontogenetic variability, the identity of the newly collected specimen, and the generic diagnostics of *Heteronebo* (*vs. Aposanguis*). Further formal studies are warranted.

Results

Due to technical and temporal constraints, combined with the poor condition of the specimens, the provided photographs are suboptimal, and not all specimens were completely digitized. Anatomical photographs were taken by manually adjusting the focal plane using the Leica microscope with an attached camera. Habitus photographs taken with a Canon camera in a single shot include a ruler (**Figs. 1–2**), enabling direct size comparison after rescaling (**Fig. 3**). Meristic characters such as PTC and TSSC were not corroborated herein, as they are unlikely to have been inaccurately documented by O. F. Francke. Given MW's limited availability, VT only requested specific photographs of crucial diagnostic characters ambiguously described in prior works: (1) dorsal and ventral habitus photographs to capture the overall profile, including pedipalp and metasomal carinae; (2) external and ventrointernal views of the chela to visualize carinae and geometry; (3) an external view of the pedipalp patella to depict its sagittal contour (curvature of the dorsal surface); (4) lateral and ventral aspects of the metasoma to specifically highlight metasomal carinae, the ventral surface of metasoma V, and telson morphology; and (5) individual images of sternite VII and the pedipalp movable finger. The immature male specimen (not type) examined by Francke (1977) was not discovered in the specimen storage room during the present visit to NHMUK.

The taxonomic history of the genus *Heteronebo* Pocock, 1899 *sensu lato*, along with the first review of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* by Francke (1977), is detailed in Tang (2025) and thus omitted here. This supplementary article only addresses key issues raised in the prior work: the species diagnostics of the two Socotran *Heteronebo* species and their presumed synonymy, the generic diagnostics of *Heteronebo* and their reliability in distinguishing

this genus from *Aposanguis*, and the potential identity of the newly collected immature specimen examined in Tang (2025).

In contrast to Francke (1978), who considered all type specimens as adults, only the lectotypes of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* are herein deemed adults, based on clear morphological distinctions from their respective paralectotypes. The paralectotype of *H. forbesii* is approximately two to three instars younger than its lectotype, while that of *H. granti* is likely at its penultimate instar, inferred from size increases observed in captive *Nebo* species (VT, pers. obs.). Nevertheless, it turned out that Francke's (1977) hand drawings quite accurately depicted the general pedipalp morphology of both species. The following discussion compares only the lectotypes.

Inspection of pedipalp morphology alone refutes the synonymy proposed by Tang (2025) between *H. forbesii* and *H. granti*. The species exhibit distinct chela morphology (**Fig. 4**), particularly in carina development: *H. granti* is characterized by a strongly costate, infuscated digital carina, whereas it is vestigial in *H. forbesii*, weakly visible only near the fixed finger base. Similarly, the external secondary carina is more developed in *H. granti* (*vs. obsolete* in *H. forbesii*), though not darkened. The inner surface carinae and dorsal marginal carina are also more granulated in *H. granti*. However, the ventromedian carina in *H. forbesii* is not as weak as depicted in Francke (1977: fig. 11). Carina differences extend to the pedipalp patella (**Fig. 6**), where retrodorsal and retroventral carinae are obsolete in *H. forbesii* but prominent in *H. granti* (especially the latter carina). A more convex dorsal surface and a greater relative depth of patella seen in Francke (1977: fig. 8) are confirmed for *H. forbesii*.

Several additional distinctions noted by Francke were verified. A more pronounced interocular sulcus in *H. forbesii* is evident,

even in the low-resolution habitus photograph (Fig. 3). The two pairs of carinae on sternite VII are slightly more developed in the lectotype of *H. forbesii* than in *H. granti*, supporting Francke's observation. However, these carinae are more prominent in the younger paralectotype of *H. granti*, challenging their phenotypic stability. Most metasomal carinae (dorsosubmedian, dorsolateral, median lateral, and ventrolateral) are stronger in *H. granti*, with a stronger distal tubercle on the dorsosubmedian carina (Fig. 7). Telson ratiometrics could not be estimated owing to the broken aculeus tip in *H. granti*, but this structure indeed appears more bulbous in *H. forbesii* (i.e., lower ratiometrics). Nevertheless, observations of multiple adult specimens of a Tibetan *Scorpiops* species indicate potential intraspecific variability in telson shape (VT, pers. obs.), thus more specimens are needed to confirm this character's reliability.

Ontogenetic variation was primarily assessed for *H. granti* as the paralectotype of *H. forbesii* was not fully photographed due to time constraint and its dilapidated condition. Comparison of *H. granti* lectotype and paralectotype confirmed the stability of the following diagnostic characters: prominent digital carina of the manus, retroventral carina of the patella, and dorsosubmedian and dorsolateral carinae of the metasoma; strong granulation on the manus inner surface; a distal tubercle on the dorsosubmedian carina; and a relatively elongated telson. The juvenile *H. forbesii* exhibits a weakly carinate metasoma and more bulbous telson (Fig. 8) along with an apparently vestigial digital carina on its manus, congruous with its adult counterpart.

Based on these findings, the revised diagnostic comparison for the two species using the presumably most reliable characters is as follows: (1) digital carina of pedipalp manus strongly costate in *H. granti* vs. vestigial in *H. forbesii*; (2) dorsal marginal carina and inner surface near the fixed finger base of pedipalp manus more prominently granulated in *H. granti*; (3) retrodorsal and retroventral carinae of pedipalp patella strongly costate in *H. granti* vs. obsolete in *H. forbesii*; (4) pedipalp patella deeper with a strongly convex dorsal surface in *H. forbesii*; (5) interocular sulcus deeper in *H. forbesii*; (6) all metasomal carinae, except ventrosubmedian and ventromedian, plus a distal tubercle, more developed in *H. granti*; (7) telson apparently more bulbous with a proportionally longer aculeus in *H. forbesii*.

The reaffirmed validity of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti*, however, raises further uncertainty about the identity of the immature specimen examined in Tang (2025). This juvenile aligns with *H. granti* in pedipalp characters, but appears closer to *H. forbesii* in metasoma and telson. Although a pronounced distal tubercle on the metasomal carinae unequivocally matches *H. granti*, carina prominence and telson ratiometrics resemble juvenile *H. forbesii*. Two most plausible explanations exist:

- (1) The juvenile, significantly smaller than NHMUK specimens, is likely at the third or fourth instar, suggesting ontogenetic variation in metasoma and telson characters (6–7). Hence, these are not universally diagnostic across all developmental stages for the two species. **Identity:** *H. granti*.
- (2) Collected from Socotra Island (vs. the types from Abd-al-Kuri Island), its discordant characters may indicate a new species. **Identity:** *H. sp. n.*

Resolving these conundrums requires additional specimens of *H. forbesii*, *H. granti*, and *H. sp.* (Socotra Island) for comparison. The first hypothesis appears more likely, given the juvenile's strong concordance with *H. granti* in most diagnostic characters. This new specimen will be donated to NHMUK in September or October 2025, pending curator availability.

The present investigation prompted a reappraisal of the generic distinctions between *Heteronebo* and *Aposanguis* (a provisional genus encompassing all Caribbean taxa currently placed under *Heteronebo*). Tang (2025) proposed the following diagnostic characters: (1) pectinal tooth count (7–10 in *Heteronebo* vs. 5–8 in *Aposanguis*); (2) chela manus shape; (3) dorsal secondary carina of chela; (4) subaculear tubercle shape; (5) metasomal carinae; (6) chela finger dentition and microsetae. Characters 2–4 and 6 are herein refuted. The chela manus in the types of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* is not proximally angular with a straight dorsal margin carina, as observed in the new juvenile specimen (hereafter referred to as *H. sp.*); adults of both species exhibit a lobiform chela, similar to most *Aposanguis* species. Although the strong digital carina in both *H. granti* specimens maintains the angular transition between dorsal and external planes seen in *H. sp.*, its absence in *H. forbesii* invalidates it as a generic diagnostic, which displays a smoother transition akin to many *Aposanguis* species. The dorsal secondary carina, while indeed vestigial (but not entirely absent) in *Heteronebo*, lacks consistent distinction from *Aposanguis*, particularly when compared to *A. bermudezi*, *A. cicero*, *A. dominicus*, *A. oviedo*, and *A. pumilus*. The telson subaculear tubercle in both *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* is bluntly triangular, not apically truncated as in *H. sp.*; whether this truncation represents an anomaly, a species trait, or ontogenetic variation remains unclear. The finger dentition in both *H. granti* types lacks the proximal denticle enlargement showed by *H. sp.* (Fig. 5), yet still does not align with *Nebo* conditions. Microsetae in the two types are denser than in *H. sp.*, though nonetheless relatively short. Some differences in denticle size and microsetae density are noticeable compared to the adult male *A. barahonae*, but their consistency at the genus level is indeterminate. The only valid qualitative trait pertains to the morphology of metasomal carinae on segments I–IV, which are costate in *Heteronebo* but granular in *Aposanguis*. No other discernible differences are evident from the available photographs. The reliance on only two characters (1 and 5) weakens the presumed distinction between *Heteronebo* and *Aposanguis*.

This study confirms the taxonomic validity of *H. forbesii* and *H. granti* and challenges the new genus proposed by Tang (2025). It underscores the importance of incorporating photographs in descriptions, examining adults, and relying on real specimens to derive taxonomic conclusions when ambiguity exists in outdated characterizations. Since both articles are informally published given the currently insufficient information on those enigmatic taxa, the generic composition of *Heteronebo* remains unchanged but still warrants further investigations considering their overall distributional disjunction (Socotra vs. Caribbean).

Acknowledgements

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Figure 1. *Heteronebo forbesii* Pocock, 1899. Row: lectotype and paralectotype females. Column: habitus in dorsal and ventral views. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 2. *Heteronebo granti* Pocock, 1899. Row: lectotype and paralectotype females. Column: habitus in dorsal and ventral views. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 3. Size comparison of inspected female materials of *Heteronebo* spp. from Yemen. Scale bar = 20 mm.

Figure 4. Pedipalp chelae. Row: *Heteronebo forbesii* lectotype, *H. granti* lectotype, and *H. granti* paralectotype. Column: aspects in external and ventrointernal views. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 5. *Heteronebo granti* pedipalp movable finger under UV light. Row: lectotype, lectotype, and paralectotype. The lectotype was photographed twice. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 6. Row: *Heteronebo forbesii* lectotype, *H. granti* lectotype, and *H. granti* paralectotype. Column: pedipalp patella in external view and sternite VII. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 7. Lectotypes. Row: *Heteronebo forbesii* metasoma in lateral view, *H. forbesii* metasoma in ventral view, *H. granti* metasoma in lateral view, *H. granti* metasoma in ventral view, and *H. forbesii* (left) and *H. granti* (right) telsons in lateral view. The telson of *H. forbesii* is not strictly lateral and part of the ventral surface was revealed proximally. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 8. Paralectotypes. Row: *Heteronebo forbesii* metasoma in lateral view, *H. granti* metasoma in lateral view, and *H. granti* metasoma in ventral view. Photos by M. Wang.

Figure 9. New *Heteronebo* specimen scheduled to be donated to NHMUK in September or October 2025. Photo by V. Tang.

Dorsal habitus with scale bar

Chela external

Metasoma lateral & ventral

Chela ventrointernal

Sternite VII

Movable finger UV

Patella (leveled) external

Figure 10. Montage of the new specimen using raw photographs.

Bonus scene

Photos by M. Wang.